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Nanoparticles and Glycosaminoglycans: Progress and Applications for Cancer Therapy

Pietro Milesi¹ | Annamaria Naggi² | Francesca Baldelli Bombelli¹ | Martin Götte^{3,4} | Jessica Oyie Sousa Onyeisi³

¹SupraBioNanoLab, Department of Chemistry, Materials, and Chemical Engineering “Giulio Natta”, Politecnico di Milano, Milano, Italy | ²Institute for Chemical and Biochemical Research “G. Ronzoni”, Milan, Italy | ³Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, University Hospital Münster, Münster, Germany | ⁴Cells-in-Motion Interfaculty Centre (CiMIC), University of Münster, Münster, Germany

Correspondence: Jessica Oyie Sousa Onyeisi (jessicaoyie@uni-muenster.de)

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ABSTRACT

Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) play essential roles in biological processes such as cell signaling and extracellular matrix assembly. Alterations in the structure of GAGs have been implicated in cancer pathogenesis, demonstrating their potential as biomarkers for cancer diagnosis and progression, as well as targets for pharmacological interventions. For these reasons, GAGs have been attracting considerable interest for potential applications in cancer therapies. On the one side, GAGs are optimal targeting sites for drug delivery systems enhancing their specificity, but on the other side, these interactions can also alter the function and cellular uptake of therapeutics. This is particularly true for nanoscaled therapeutics. This review aims at highlighting the role of the GAGs in regulating the cellular uptake of nanoparticles (NPs) and of the exploitation of NP–GAG interactions for effective drug delivery, particularly in targeting cancer cells. We will include relevant examples of GAG-functionalized NPs for their potential in targeted drug delivery, imaging, and theranostic applications, showing that GAG stabilization can prevent agglomeration and improve functionality.

1 | Introduction

Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) are linear, negatively charged heteropolysaccharides composed of repeating disaccharide units of *N*-acetylated hexosamine and uronic acid [1, 2]. Differences in the type of monosaccharide in the repeating units as well as their sulfation result in the following major categories of GAGs: hyaluronan/hyaluronic acid (HA), chondroitin sulfate (CS) and dermatan sulfate (DS), heparin and heparan sulfate (HS) and keratan sulfate. While HA is synthesized at the cell membrane, GAGs like HS and CS/DS are synthesized on GAG-attachment sites on core proteins in a series of enzyme reactions involving polymerization of the repetitive disaccharide backbone and extensive modification (epimerization, sulfation, deacetylation). GAGs are among the most structurally complex carbohydrates found in nature [3–5].

GAGs play multiple roles as signal molecules regulating protein activity while also functioning as structural components and effectors of cellular activity. In addition, they have been shown to modulate numerous biological processes [6–10], ranging from embryonic development, regulation of enzymatic activities, extracellular matrix assembly, ligand binding to receptors and the regulation of cell signaling, through the regulation of distinct proteins, such as growth factors, chemokines, and adhesion molecules (Table 1) [7, 12–15]. These processes are particularly important when related to diseases, including infectious diseases, neurodegenerative disorders, and cancer. GAGs play distinct roles in various stages of tumor progression, significantly contributing to cell invasion, migration, angiogenesis, differentiation, and immune modulation. The deregulation of enzymes involved in GAG synthesis or

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TABLE 1 | Main roles of GAGs in biological processes.

Glycosaminoglycan (GAG)	Biological function	References
Heparin	Anticoagulant	[6]
	Antithrombotic	[11]
	Anti-inflammatory properties	[7]
Heparan sulfate (HS)	Regulation of Inflammatory responses	[12]
	Involvement in bacterial and viral infections	[8]
	Role in embryonic development and blood coagulation	[9]
Chondroitin sulfate (CS)/Dermatan sulfate	Promotion of neurite outgrowth and axonal regeneration	[13]
	Wound healing	[14]
	Regulation of growth factors signaling	[14]
Hyaluronic acid (HA)	Dual roles in pro and anti-inflammatory processes	[15]
	Promotion or inhibition of cell migration and proliferation	[15]
	Exhibiting immunosuppressive activities	[16]

FIGURE 1 | Role of glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) in promoting cancer development and progression. GAGs are linear, negatively charged heteropolysaccharides, composed of repeating disaccharide units that consist of an amino sugar (D-glucosamine, i.e., N-acetylated, or N-sulfated, or N-acetyl-D-galactosamine) and either uronic acid (D-glucuronic acid or L-iduronic acid). The major categories of GAGs are: heparin, heparan sulfate (HS), chondroitin sulfate (CS), dermatan sulfate (DS), and hyaluronic acid (HA). GAGs affect different aspects in cancer initiation, progression, and treatment.

degradation, as well as aberrant expression and fine structure of GAGs and proteoglycans (PGs) can promote cancer development and progression [17–21] (Figure 1). Considering the involvement of GAGs in tumor development, they have attracted considerable interest for potential applications in anticancer therapies. GAGs can serve not only as targeting sites, but also as key enhancers for drug delivery systems, taking advantage of their specificity and exceptional physicochemical properties to enable, for example, precise delivery of cancer

therapeutics [19, 22, 23]. Among these drug delivery systems, nanoparticles (NPs) have emerged as promising vehicles for cancer treatment [24].

Nanoparticles are definite objects with sizes on the nanometer length scale that can be made of different materials (organic and inorganic) determining their physicochemical properties (Figure 2). In particular, the surface of NPs can generally be functionalized with various chemical groups and biomolecules

FIGURE 2 | A comprehensive scheme of types of nanoparticles. Based on their composition, NPs can be classified into three classes: organic, carbon-based, and inorganic.

(i.e., peptides, proteins, carbohydrates, etc.), which allows to target specific cells [25]. Depending on the nature of their core, NPs can be used to encapsulate either hydrophobic small molecules or hydrophilic macromolecules (e.g., nucleic acids) [26, 27] (Figure 2). Nanoparticles can be programmed to release their payload in response to different biological and external stimuli, including pH, temperature, and electromagnetic fields [28]. Several methods have been developed for the toxicity testing of NPs, many of which are also employed in modern drug development. The toxicity of NPs has been evaluated using both two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) spheroid cell cultures. Notably, the introduction of 3D-cell-culture models for NP toxicity testing revealed significant differences when compared to conventional 2D cell culture models [29–31].

This review is focused on the interaction of GAGs with NPs, emphasizing the importance of bio–nano interactions occurring at extracellular level and how these interactions can affect NP uptake, specifically in the perspective to use them in cancer therapy. Moreover, we will discuss the roles of GAGs in targeted drug delivery, summarizing the extensive work done on GAG-functionalized NPs to enhance specificity and efficacy in targeting cancer cells. We will also report the use of GAG–NP in imaging and diagnostic applications, particularly focusing on their ability to improve the contrast and specificity of imaging techniques.

1.1 | Glycosaminoglycans: Structure and Function

1.1.1 | Heparin

Heparin is the most highly sulfated GAG. Its molecular weight (MW) ranges from 5 to 30 kDa. It is composed of 1→4 linked disaccharide repeating units consisting of an α -D-glucosamine (A) and a hexuronic acid (either α -L-iduronic (I) or β -D-glucuronic (G) acid). Most of the 2-position of iduronic acid and of the 2- and 6-positions of glucosamine are sulfated. In a minority of glucosamine residues, the position 3 is sulfated [32]. Apart from its well-established anticoagulant and antithrombotic effects, heparin has anti-inflammatory properties, that

are mechanistically related to the inhibition of leukocyte adhesion and migration, and the modulation of cytokine production [33, 34]. Several studies demonstrate that heparin and its low molecular weight (LMW) derivatives can inhibit neutrophil adhesion to activated endothelial cells (ECs) by binding to selectin, and thereby block acute inflammation. Heparin has also been shown to compete with HS, and to effectively inhibit the enzymatic activity of heparanase (HPSE), an endoglucuronidase involved in inflammation and cancer progression [35–37]. The more bioavailable and less anticoagulant low-molecular-weight heparin (LMWH) appears to prolong the survival of cancer patients. In published randomized controlled trials, four different types of LMWH increased the survival of patients with advanced cancer [11, 38, 39]. Indeed, rather than preventing fatal pulmonary emboli in cancer patients, it seems more likely that LMWH has direct effects on tumor growth and metastasis [40, 41].

Heparin can inhibit cancer progression through the inhibition of HPSE, an enzyme able to cleave HS chains into smaller fragments, which can retain bioactivity. HPSE is overexpressed in various cancers, facilitating tumor cell extravasation and metastasis [42]. Heparin modulates cell adhesion by inhibiting selectins, such as P- and L-selectins, which have also been shown to promote tumor metastasis [43, 44]. Heparin has a high affinity to tumor cells through binding to clotted plasma proteins (fibrinogen-derived product) in the stroma [45] and growth factors. Furthermore, heparin might be recruited into the tumor tissue overexpressing heparin-binding angiogenic growth factors [46, 47]

The use of native heparin as a therapeutic agent is limited due to its potent anticoagulant activity. Therefore, nonanticoagulant heparins possess clinical potential, as they can be administered at high doses where the use of heparin is precluded [48, 49].

1.1.2 | Heparan Sulfate

HS is a macromolecule composed of repetitive disaccharide units similar to those of heparin, but with a lower degree of sulfation. Initially discovered as a by-product of heparin

isolation, over time it has proven to be a ubiquitous component of tissues and organs [50–52]. The polymeric structure of HS is characterized by a regular alternation of sequences of highly sulfated regions called S-domains, with *N*-acetylated regions (NA domains) of very low sulfation [53]. In addition to these two main domains, another type of sequence composed of alternating *N*-acetylated and *N*-sulfated disaccharide units named NA/NS domains is present in the transition zones between the sulfated and acetylated domains [54]. The great variability observed between HS from different cells and tissues depends on the proportion of these three domains and the resulting sulfation density, which is reflected in their biological properties. A large number of proteins and peptides bind to HS molecules and form the so-called HS “interactome” [55]. HS-PGs are components of extracellular matrix and cell membrane. Through their ability to bind and modulate the function of several HS-binding proteins, they have a pivotal role in cancer growth and progression (inflammation, proliferation, angiogenesis, and metastasis) [56]. They mediate the concentration of cytokines at the cell surface [57], which stimulate the migration and extravasation of neutrophils and lymphocytes in the context of inflammation, they control the diffusion of morphogenic proteins during embryogenesis [58], and regulate enzymes involved in coagulation processes and lipid metabolism [59].

Despite its great potential, HS, unlike heparin, has never become a major drug, except for its presence in Danaparoid [60] which has a HS content between 78.0% and 87.2%. Indeed, its isolation is not economically viable, in contrast to heparin.

In fact, unlike heparin, HS is widely distributed in various organs and tissues and its isolation does not have the same yield. To overcome the difficulty of its supply, various mimetics have been proposed, obtained either through the chemical modification of heparin or its biosynthetic precursor heparosan, obtained via fermentation [61–64] or through chemical [65] and chemoenzymatic synthesis [66, 67].

1.1.3 | Chondroitin Sulfate/Dermatan Sulfate (CS/DS)

CS is the major GAG in cartilage. It is present in a variety of tissues linked to several core proteins to form PGs, which perform important physiological functions during embryonic development, in cell proliferation, skin hydration, and structural functions in tissues. CS is made of repeating units of glucuronic (GlcA) or iduronic (IdoA), and amino sugars, *N*-acetyl-galactosamine (GalNAc) linked by $\beta(1\rightarrow3)$ bonds. Historically, three types of chondroitins have been distinguished: A, B, and C. CS-A and CS-C are mainly composed of disaccharides sulfated in position C4 or C6 of the GalNAc residue, respectively, with a minor percentage of the monosulfated disaccharide on C2 of GlcA. Besides these, minor components can also include sulfate groups in various percentages in other positions, depending on the animal source [68]. CS-B or DS is made up of disaccharide units of iduronic acid (IdoA) and GalNAc mainly sulfated in position C4 with a minor percent of disaccharides disulfated in position in C4 and C2 of GalNAc, and also of nonsulfated GlcA [69]. The combination of the different repeating units, which determine the degree of

sulfation and the mobility of the polymer chain, means that a large number of CSs with various specialized biological functions are present in nature [70]. CS is present in all mammalian connective tissues, particularly in cartilage, ligaments, tendons, blood vessels, and skin [71]. CS participates in the cellular processes of adhesion, differentiation, morphogenesis, organogenesis and the formation of the neuronal network [72, 73]. Treatment with CS has been reported to improve osteoarthritis symptoms and to reduce the disease [14, 74–76].

DS is ubiquitous in the extracellular matrix and the major glycan present in skin, representing ~0.3% of its dry weight. DS is involved in the coagulation cascade through the interaction with heparin factor II (HCII) which inhibits the procoagulant effect of thrombin [77]. It also influences coagulation processes by enhancing the effects of activated protein C [76] and the dermatan chains in the decorin PG bind LDL involved in atherosclerotic processes [78].

1.1.4 | Hyaluronan (HA)

Hyaluronan (HA) is the only nonsulfated GAG, it is formed of alternating units of *D*-glucuronic acid (GlcA) and *N*-acetyl-*D*-glucosamine (GlcNAc), connected to each other with β -1,3- and β -1,4-glycosidic bonds: $[\rightarrow4)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-GlcA-(1}\rightarrow3)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-GlcNAc-(1)}$. Like all GAGs, it is a linear polydisperse polymer, characterized by a high molecular weight (HMW): its MW can range from 20 to 4000 kDa. In mammals, it is found mainly as space filler of the extracellular matrix, in eye vitreous humor, in synovial liquid, and in loose connective tissue [16, 79] with a maximum content in skin, intestine, and lung [80, 81]. In addition to its main function of hydrating tissues, it binds numerous proteins to both in the extracellular matrix and on the cell surfaces. The most studied HA-binding protein is, in the cartilage, the PG aggrecan [82], but in a similar way it binds other macromolecules such as hyaluronectin, neurocan, decorin, lumican, laminin, fibronectin, fibrinogen, hyaluronan-mediated motility receptor and the transmembrane protein CD44 [83, 84].

HMW HA has been reported to possess anti-inflammatory [85] antiangiogenic and immunosuppressive activity [86]. It has been hypothesized that this effect arises in part from the capacity of the molecule to cover the exterior of cells to prevent access of ligands to surface receptors [87]. Hyaluronan of lower molecular size mediates wound healing processes [88] chondrogenesis, infection, and cancer. In the case of cancer, the function of the HA molecule depends on its MW. LMW HA increases the adhesion capacity of fibrosarcoma cells, promoting the metastatic tumor dissemination, whereas HMW HA has an opposite effect [89]. LMW HA and HA oligosaccharides smaller than 36 kDa (100 disaccharides units) induce proteolytic cleavage of CD44 on the surface of cancer cells stimulating tumor cell migration, and tumor progression in gliomas, breast, colon, and ovarian cancers, and in non-small cell carcinomas of the lung [90, 91]. On the contrary, it was reported that the HA tetrasaccharides obtained by exhaustive enzymatic digestion with sheep testicular hyaluronidase (HAase) had no angiogenic effect [92, 93]. Due to its strong binding ability to bind cancer cells, HA has been used as a carrier for tumor drugs [94].

2 | Glycocalyx Effects on NP Cellular Internalization

There are several studies on the role of the glycocalyx on NP cellular uptake reporting different outcomes depending on the size and charge of the NPs. For example, the group of Sousa and colleagues showed that the highly anionic GAG components of the glycocalyx form a charge-based barrier toward the cellular internalization of negatively charged polystyrene NPs of 50 nm. They showed that the addition of enzymes to the cell media cleaving either HS or CS produced a strong increase of NP uptake. Contrarily, they observed that the cellular uptake of positively charged polystyrene NPs was reduced upon cleavage of HS, but not CS, implying a specific interaction of the former with these NPs [95]. Another study on HeLa cells on positively charged gold NPs of a size ranging from 2 to 7 nm showed that enzymatic digestion of the glycocalyx affected the cellular uptake of the NPs [96]. In particular, the authors found that the addition of HS-degrading heparinase III induced a significant increase in NP cellular uptake, while the addition of neuroamidase, affecting glycoproteins and glycolipids, produced a reduction in NP internalization indicating different interactions of the specific components of the glycocalyx with these NPs. Contrarily, the cellular uptake of citrate-coated iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs), characterized by a slight negative charge, by phagocytic cells did not show dependence on the GAGs indicating that CS, HS and HA are not strong binders of these NPs [97].

In summary, the glycocalyx significantly influences the cellular uptake of surface-charged NPs. However, the final outcomes can be heavily affected by both characteristics of the NPs, the type of the protein corona that adsorbs on NP surface, and the type of cells involved (Figure 3), highlighting the need for targeted studies in this area [98].

3 | GAG-Functionalized NPs can Target the Tumor Microenvironment

GAG-based NPs are considered promising drug delivery systems in tumor therapy thanks to their biocompatibility and CD44-targeting ability. In particular, CD44 is overexpressed in tumor cells [94] and can selectively bind GAGs such as HA and CS [99]. Both HA and CS have been chemically linked to hydrophobic drugs, obtaining prodrugs, that were specifically released in the tumor microenvironment (TME) thanks to enzymatic degradation, and selectively internalized in cancer cells through CD44 recognition [100, 101]. Alternatively, GAGs have been chemically and physically adsorbed to the surface of different NPs [102] encapsulating hydrophobic drugs, thus promoting their biocompatibility and their ability to target cancer cells. Many studies combine targeting with the degradation action of hyaluronidase for promoting the release of encapsulated drugs. These approaches have been extensively used to develop CS/HA-based delivery systems with potential applications for chemotherapy, photodynamic therapy (PTT) and gene for cancer treatment [103–107].

FIGURE 3 | Impact of the glycocalyx on cellular internalization of NPs. The properties of the NPs (including charge and size) and the specific components of the glycocalyx contribute to the regulation of NP internalization. NPs, nanoparticles; HS, heparan sulfate; CS, chondroitin sulfate.

Micellar NPs often expose slow and deficient drug release at the pathological site, leading to compromised therapeutic effects [108]. They have hydrophilic and hydrophobic compartments [109]. Carvalho and colleagues described a novel method to produce micellar NPs with a GAG shell, such as HA or CS, as potential drug delivery systems targeting cancer cells that overexpress CD44. The study demonstrated that the GAGs exposed on the nanoparticle surface were bioactive, interacting specifically with CD44 cell receptors, thereby ensuring targeted delivery of the encapsulated therapeutic agents [109]. HA nanoparticles exhibit greater encapsulation efficiency and physiologically relevant redox-responsiveness, making them more suitable for tumor-targeting delivery systems. In contrast, CS nanoparticles form larger and less compact assemblies due to higher charge density and repulsion caused by sulfate groups and longer chains. An internalization assay was performed on two human breast cancer cell lines with differing levels of CD44 expression: MDA-MB-468, which overexpresses CD44, and SKBR-3, which lacks CD44 expression. The results indicated that only MDA-MB-468 cells effectively internalized both types of nanoparticles. HA-based assemblies emerge as promising nanotheranostic tools for targeting CD44-overexpressing cancer cells [110, 111].

Further studies have provided additional insights into optimizing HA NPs (HA-NPs) for drug delivery. Choi and colleagues synthesized HA nanoparticles with different diameters by adjusting the degree of hydrophobic modification of HA. These nanoparticles were systemically administered to tumor-bearing mice, and their effects were evaluated. The study demonstrated that HA-NPs selectively targeted tumor tissues through both passive accumulation via the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect and active targeting mediated by the strong receptor-binding affinity of HA to CD44, achieving high specificity *in vivo* [112]. Another study developed a versatile thermostatic system using poly (ethylene glycol)-conjugated HA nanoparticles (P-HA-NPs) for the early detection of colon cancer and targeted therapy. These nanoparticles were conjugated with the near-infrared fluorescent dye Cy5.5 and encapsulated with the anticancer drug irinotecan (IRT). The therapeutic potential of P-HA-NPs was evaluated in different mouse models of colon cancer, showing promising results [113].

Some tumors (e.g., non-small cell lung cancer, pancreatic adenocarcinoma, etc.) are characterized by denser stroma made of protein networks and GAGs, which represents an additional barrier for the NPs to penetrate the tumor tissues. However, this complex extracellular matrix has been used as a target to ensure NP-mediated drug delivery. In particular, Kuo and colleagues have shown that the functionalization of doxorubicin-loaded liposomes with a cell-penetrating peptide with high affinity to HS strongly increased tumor accumulation in lung adenocarcinoma xenograft models with a consequent increase of the therapeutic efficacy [114]. Moreover, peptide-modified liposomes showed HS-mediated uptake and a higher penetration degree in tumor spheroids with respect to unmodified PEGylated liposomes, which mostly localized at the periphery of the organoids. Heparin has been also used for targeting the TME, in particular LWMH, for its high affinity to different overexpressed components such as angiogenic growth factors [46]. During past

decades, several heparin/heparin derivatives have been used to prepare tumor-targeted nanocarriers. These nanocarriers mainly are divided in two classes: (i) heparin-based polymeric derivatives [115–117] and (ii) core-shell nanoparticles composed of a hydrophobic core and a hydrophilic heparin shell [118, 119]. Moreover, heparin—being highly negatively charged—can also be complexed with polycations forming polyelectrolyte nanoparticles. A recent work reports on indocyanine green (ICG)-loaded liposomes functionalized on the surface by LMWH for phototherapy [120], significantly enhancing antitumoral efficacy by reducing the adhesion of platelets to tumor cells and inhibiting the migration of these cells. These properties have been largely used to develop hybrid GAG-functionalized metal NPs for different biomedical applications as it is summarized in the next sections.

Poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) is a widely used linear copolymer in controlled drug delivery systems, with adjustable ratios between its constituent monomers, lactic acid (LA) and glycolic acid (GA) [121, 122]. Chitosan and heparin were incorporated into PLGA microparticles (P/C-h) to enhance the cellular functions of human mesenchymal stem cell (hMSC) aggregates. The P/C-h composite microparticles were fabricated using a combination of double emulsion and microfluidic technology, allowing precise control of the emulsion composition and the flow rate of the two phases in a flow-focusing chip. The incorporation of P/C-h composite microparticles maintained the stemness and cell activity of hMSCs within the aggregates. These P/C-h composite microparticles hold potential as drug delivery systems for the 3D culture of hMSCs in regenerative medicine. Moreover, they are particularly suitable for supporting 3D stem cell aggregate culture and for integrating targeted functionalities into *in vitro* organ-on-a-chip models [31, 123]. A summary of the results is illustrated in Figure 4.

4 | Iron Oxide Nanoparticles Functionalized With GAGs for Advanced Imaging

IONPs are a class of magnetic nanoparticles that have been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for clinical use [124, 125]. IONPs can be composed of either mixed iron oxide phases, or a single iron oxide phase, such as magnetite. They are generally characterized by low toxicity and high biocompatibility rendering them suitable for various biomedical applications. Due to these advantageous properties, IONPs have been the focus of extensive research, leading to significant advancements, particularly in the field of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). IONPs below a critical diameter (≈ 30 nm) behave as single-domain magnets with superparamagnetic properties [126, 127] and they are called superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs). The SPIONs are often coated with organic or inorganic materials that allow for drug loading. There are three types of iron oxides that may form the cores of a SPION: magnetite (Fe_3O_4), maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), and hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$). The SPIONs can be directed to specific tissues using an external magnetic field, a critical feature for biomedical applications [128]. The unique properties of SPIONs have enabled their use in a broad range of applications, including as MRI contrast agents, multimodal imaging, ferrofluid technology for thermotherapy, targeted drug delivery, cancer tumor

GAGs functionalized NPs can target the tumor microenvironment

FIGURE 4 | GAG-functionalized NPs can target the tumor microenvironment. (A) Micellar NPs with a GAG shell and HA NPs were produced as potential drug delivery systems targeting cancer cells that overexpress CD44. (B) Heparin and chitosan were incorporated into PLGA microparticles to enhance the cellular functions of human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs). (C) In liposomes loaded with doxorubicin, a high affinity to HS strongly increased tumor accumulation in lung adenocarcinoma. NPs, nanoparticles; PLGA, poly (D, L-lactide-co-glycolide) acid; HA, hyaluronic acid; CS, chondroitin sulfate.

detection via superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometry, gene therapy, biomolecular separation, in vivo biomolecular detection, and tissue repair [129]. Advancements in nanoparticle synthesis have led to the development of very small monomer-coated SPIONs (e.g., citrate-coated) called very small superparamagnetic iron oxide particles (VSOPs), with diameters ranging from 7 to 10 nm [130]. These VSOPs, characterized by a citrate coating and a negative surface charge, contain a 5 nm iron oxide core. Their small size enhances cellular uptake without the need for additional transfection agents and viability [13]. Recent studies have demonstrated that the aggregation of VSOPs on the surface of a monocytic cell is mediated by GAG chains of PGs present on the cell surface [131]. Furthermore, altered sulfated GAGs on inflamed brain ECs serve as the primary binding site for the electrostatically stabilized VSOP during inflammation, suggesting potential implications for targeted therapeutic applications [132, 133].

Given their unique magnetic properties and biocompatibility, one of the most significant applications of IONPs is in imaging technologies. Here, we will focus on the utilization of GAG-

functionalized IONPs for cancer imaging. The interactions and applications of magnetic nanoparticles in these contexts are critically influenced by their material composition and structural characteristics, including particle size, morphology, surface charge, and specific surface modifications [134].

MRI is a powerful clinical imaging modality that provides high-resolution 3D images of small tumors and metastases. Paramagnetic materials, including stable Gd(III) chelates and SPIONs, are often used as contrast agents to increase the T_1 and T_2 relaxation rates of water protons in the tissues of interest and to produce contrast enhancement for diagnostic imaging [135]. Despite the continuous efforts in developing novel MRI contrast agents, there is a serious lack of safe and effective targeted contrast agents for high-sensitivity molecular MRI in clinical practice. Li and colleagues developed a polyethyleneimine (PEI)-mediated approach for synthesizing HA-targeted Fe_3O_4 -based SPIONs for in vivo targeted tumor MRI. Modification of hydrothermally synthesized PEI-stabilized Fe_3O_4 NPs with HA could be achieved via PEI-mediated covalent conjugation reaction. The effectiveness of these modified SPIONs for MRI imaging of a human cervical carcinoma cell line (Hela cells)

was subsequently confirmed. The coating of Fe_3O_4 NPs with PEI increases the colloidal stability and water dispersibility of the NPs [136]. Considering the strong positive charge of PEI, which raises concerns about cytotoxicity, Yang and colleagues developed a different synthetic approach for preparing HA-functionalized SPIONs for targeted MRI imaging of liver carcinoma. They modified the surface of SPIONs via HA conjugation assisted by a biocompatible amino-modified silane, thus achieving specific targeting to human hepatocellular liver carcinoma (HepG2) cells in vitro and in vivo models. This modification provided SPIONs with good water dispersibility and cytocompatibility [137]. Very small superparamagnetic iron oxide particles (VSOPs) were found promising for radiological imaging of extracellular vesicles (EVs) due to their interactions with GAGs present on the EVs. EVs isolated from the supernatants of ECs or vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) were demonstrated to interact with VSOPs in a GAG-dependent manner. Furthermore, studies have demonstrated that uremic conditions enhanced GAG contents in EVs, resulting in stronger interactions with VSOPs [138]. In addition, VSOP-based MRI enabled visualization of early inflammatory processes in neuroinflammation by detecting initial alterations in GAGs on brain ECs [133]. A summary of the results is illustrated in Figure 5.

4.1 | Iron Oxide Nanoparticles Functionalized With GAGs as Theranostic Agents

Beyond their excellent properties as imaging agents, IONPs have been widely recognized as promising materials for targeted drug delivery systems and controlled drug release [125]. Thus, there are many examples of GAG-functionalized IONP

combining the peculiar properties of the magnetic core with those of the GAG. For example, Wang and colleagues coated the surface of IONP with dopamine-modified HA to deliver the chemotherapy drug homocamptothecin (HCPT) to tumor areas in response to an external magnetic field. Their study demonstrated that dopamine-modified HA forms a stable and robust coating on the IONP surface, imparting excellent biocompatibility, biostability, and tumor-targeting capabilities to the HA-IONP complex. By applying an external magnetic field, the fraction of IONPs reaching the tumor site after systemic administration was significantly increased, thereby strongly improving the biodistribution of the chemotherapeutic agent at the tumor location. The HA functionalization has enhanced binding to CD44 which is overexpressed in tumor cells. This strategy significantly increases the effectiveness and specificity of cancer treatment [139]. Similarly, Vismara and colleagues designed a theranostic nanosystem composed of a SPION core functionalized with both HA and bovine serum albumin (BSA), covalently conjugated to dopamine (DA), which served as an anchoring mechanism to the SPIONs. The resulting DA-BSA/HA SPIONs were successfully loaded with paclitaxel (PTX), and a controlled, gradual release of the drug was observed over time, indicating the potential of DA-BSA/HA SPIONs as an effective theranostic agent [140]. An analog strategy was employed to engineer SPIONs with an organic coating composed of LMWH and BSA, creating a heparin-based SPION (LMWH@SPIONs). In this system, BSA was used to enhance biocompatibility and reduce toxicity, while dopamine served as a spacer between the SPIONs and LMWH/BSA coating due to its catechol and amino groups. PTX loading efficiency, and antitumor effects of LMWH@SPIONs loaded with PTX were evaluated by in vitro experiments. The results indicated that pristine LMWH@SPIONs were not cytotoxic to HeLa cells, but when loaded with PTX, they

FIGURE 5 | Iron oxide NPs functionalized with GAGs for advanced imaging. Modification of hydrothermally synthesized PEI-stabilized Fe_3O_4 NPs with HA was achieved via PEI-mediated covalent conjugation reaction. Modified SPIONs demonstrated effectiveness in MRI imaging of a human cervical carcinoma cell line (HeLa cells) and hepatocellular liver carcinoma cells (HepG2 cells). VSOPs were found promising for radiological imaging of EVs due to their interactions with GAGs present on the EVs isolated from the supernatants of endothelial cells (ECs). PEI, polyethyleneimine; Fe_3O_4 NPs, Iron oxide NPs; HA, hyaluronic acid; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; SPIONs, superparamagnetic iron oxide NPs; EVs, extracellular vesicles; VSOP, very small iron oxide particles NPs.

exhibited a significantly higher antiproliferative activity against breast carcinoma cells (4T1 cells) compared to free PTX under the same experimental conditions [141].

The advancements in functionalizing IONPs with biocompatible polymers like HA or LMWH, and BSA highlight the significant potential of these nanomaterials as theranostic agents in cancer

treatment (Figure 6). This approach not only improves the therapeutic efficacy of chemotherapeutic agents like PTX, but also minimizes off-target effects, thereby offering a promising method for the development of next-generation cancer therapies. Future research should focus on further optimizing these nanoparticle systems to enhance their clinical applicability and expand their use in a broader range of medical applications.

FIGURE 6 | Iron oxide NPs functionalized with GAGs as theranostic agents. The surface of IONP was coated with dopamine-modified HA to deliver the chemotherapy drug homocamptothecin (HCPT) to tumor areas in response to an external magnetic field. SPIONs were functionalized with an organic coating composed of low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) and BSA, resulting in a heparin-based SPION (LMWH@SPIONs) designed to delivery of paclitaxel (PTX). The PTX loading efficiency and antitumor effects of LMWH@SPIONs loaded with PTX were evaluated by in vitro experiments. The LMWH@SPIONs significantly enhanced antiproliferative activity against breast carcinoma cells (4T1 cells) compared to free PTX. IONPs + HA, iron oxide NPs and hyaluronic acid; SPIONs + LMWH, superparamagnetic iron oxide NPs and low molecular weight heparin.

GAG-based nanosystems and applications

FIGURE 7 | Different types of self-assembled nanocarriers with GAGs as a backbone and nanoparticles with GAG as surface coating. Applications within the nanomedicine field.

TABLE 2 | Nanoparticles and glycosaminoglycans.

Application	Material	GAGs	References
Effects on NP cellular internalization	Negatively charged polystyrene nanoparticles	Cell-surface GAGs	[95]
	Positively charged gold nanoparticles	Glycocalyx components	[96]
	Citrate-coated iron oxide nanoparticles (SynC)	Hyaluronic acid Heparan sulfate Chondroitin sulfate	[97]
Targeting the tumor microenvironment	Micellar	Hyaluronic acid Chondroitin sulfate	[109]
	Hyaluronic acid	Self-assembly of hydrophobically modified hyaluronic acid Derivatives	[110, 111, 113]
	Liposomes	Peptide with high affinity to heparan sulfate	[114]
	Poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA)	Heparin	[123]
Visualization of early inflammatory processes in neuroinflammation	Very small superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (VSOPs)	GAGs present on the EVs	[131–133]
MR imaging of human cervical carcinoma cell line (Hela cells)	Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles	Hyaluronic acid	[136]
MRI of imaging of liver carcinoma	Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs)		[137]
Enhancing the efficacy and specificity of cancer treatment	Iron oxide nanoparticles (IONP)		[139]
Theranostic agent	Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs)	Low molecular weight heparin (LMWH)	[141]

5 | Conclusion and Future Perspective

GAGs play crucial roles in the pathophysiology of diverse cancers by modulating cellular interactions and extracellular matrix dynamics. This review has highlighted how GAGs enhance the specificity and stability of diverse NPs systems, influence their uptake, and function across different cell types. We believe that understanding GAG–NPs interactions and optimizing these systems may lead to highly specific cancer treatments (Figure 7). An overview of the key findings is systematically presented in Table 2.

Author Contributions

Pietro Milesi: writing and figure preparation. **Annamaria Naggi:** writing review and editing. **Francesca Baldelli Bombelli:** writing – review and editing. **Martin Götte:** supervision, funding acquisition, review and editing. **Jessica Oyie Sousa Onyeisi:** conceptualization, figure preparation, writing – original draft, data collection.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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